

Isocoumarins. Part-XXIII. Synthesis of some 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-phenylisocoumarins

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FRIEDEL-Crafts acylation of anisole, phenetole and other phenols with 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride in the presence of anhydrous AlCl_3 at boiling water-bath temperature using nitrobenzene as solvent gave directly the 6,7-dimethoxy-3-phenylisocoumarins (**1a-f**) in good yield. The condensation in presence of SnCl_4 gave the same isocoumarins.

(1a-f)

(2a-f)

- a** ; $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = \text{H}$, $R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$
b ; $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = \text{H}$, $R_3 = \text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$
c ; $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = \text{H}$, $R_3 = \text{OH}$
d ; $R_1 = \text{CH}_3$, $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$, $R_4 = \text{OH}$, $R_5 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$
e ; $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}$, $R_3 = \text{OH}$, $R_5 = \text{OCH}_3$
f ; $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}$, $R_3 = \text{CH}_3$, $R_5 = \text{OH}$

Treatment of the isocoumarin (**1a-f**) with hot aqueous NaOH opened the lactone ring and the respective ketones (**2a-f**) thus formed were cyclised

back with 80% sulphuric acid to the corresponding isocoumarins. On oxidation with alkaline KMnO_4 , the ketones (2) gave *p*-anisic acid, *p*-ethoxybenzoic acid, *p*-thymotic acid, *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid along with 3,4-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid; in case of cresols no pure product could be isolated.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The homogeneity of the compounds were ascertained by tlc on silica gel G plates. The uv spectra (MeOH) were recorded on a Hilger spectrophotometer.

A mixture of 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid¹ (5 g) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for ~1 h and then cooled to yield 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride. The anhydride was sublimed under reduced pressure, m.p. 175–76°.

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-phenylisocoumarins (1a–f). General procedure: Compounds 1a–f were prepared from the phenols, anisole, phenetole, phenol, thymol, *o*-cresol and *p*-cresol respectively.

(a) *In presence of anhydrous AlCl_3 :* A mixture of the anhydride (1.0 mol), the phenol (1.0 mol) and anhydrous AlCl_3 (1.5 mol) in dry nitrobenzene (10 ml) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 3 h. The mixture was then decomposed over crushed ice and concentrated HCl and nitrobenzene was removed by distillation. The resulting solid was triturated with aqueous NaHCO_3 , filtered, washed with water and crystallised from appropriate solvent (Table 1).

(10% ; 10 ml) for ~1 h, then cooled and treated with concentrated HCl. The solid was dissolved in aqueous NaHCO_3 , filtered and acidified. The resulting solid was crystallised from appropriate solvent as needles (Table 1).

Cyclodehydration of the ketone (2a–f) with 80% H_2SO_4 : The ketone (2a–f; 1 g) was mixed with 80% H_2SO_4 (15 ml) and left overnight. It was then poured over crushed ice. The solid obtained was washed with NaHCO_3 solution, water and crystallised from appropriate solvent, when the respective isocoumarins (1a–f) were obtained.

Oxidation of the ketone (2a–f) with alkaline KMnO_4 : A mixture of the ketone (2a–f; 1 g), KMnO_4 (2.5 g) and aqueous Na_2CO_3 (1% ; 100 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, then filtered hot and the residue washed with hot water. The filtrate and washings were concentrated and then acidified with HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water and dried. The solid was fractionally crystallised when *m*-hemipinic acid separated first, and on concentration of the mother liquor the respective acids were obtained.

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Reference

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. ** °C	λ_{max} (nm)
1a	85	217–18 ^a	233, 277, 312
1b	80	149–50 ^a	230, 273, 325
1c	80	269–70 ^b	230, 273, 325
1d	85	210–12 ^e	—
1e	80	229–31 ^d	235, 270, 325
1f	80	212–14 ^d	230, 277, 312
2a	65	206–07 ^a	—
2b	70	202–03 ^d	—
2c	60	236–38 ^a	—
2d	65	183–84 ^d	—
2e	70	242–43 ^b	—
2f	70	206–07 ^b	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Solvent for crystallisation: ^aMeOH, ^bEtOH, ^caq. MeOH, ^daq. EtOH.

(b) *In presence of anhydrous SnCl_4 :* A mixture of the anhydride (1.0 mol), the phenol (1.0 mol) and anhydrous SnCl_4 (2.0 mol) was heated in an oil-bath at 120–25° for 2 h. It was then decomposed over ice and concentrated HCl. The separated solid was boiled with HCl (1 : 1) for ~1 h, filtered, washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 and water and crystallised from appropriate solvent (Table 1).

Preparation of the ketones (2a–f): The isocoumarin (1 g) was refluxed with aqueous NaOH